

THE VARIATION OF RELATIVE VISCOSITY WITH TEMPERATURE

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A study of the temperature dependence of relative viscosity η_r/η_0 of concentrated and supersaturated aqueous solutions of electrolytes has been made. The results show that, provided viscosity remains sufficiently low, $\partial/\partial T (\eta_r/\eta_0)$ is positive even in highly concentrated solutions of some electrolytes e. g. KCl, KBr, KI and KNO_3 , etc. Further, the $\partial/\partial T (\eta_r/\eta_0)$ is comparatively much high in the solutions of substances which have low hydrating power as compared to those which easily form hydrates with water molecules. These observations have been explained with the help of Rabinowitch's hydrate hypothesis and the depolymerisation concept of Applebey.

The study of the variation of relative viscosity of solutions with temperature is important because it throws considerable light on the structure of both the solvent and solution. According to Hatschek ("Viscosity of Liquids", 1928), relative viscosity of aqueous solutions of electrolytes, referred to water at the same temperature, rises with temperature. This change is in opposite direction to that of non-electrolytes. For electrolytes the statement of Hatschek is, in general, supported by the observations of Rankine and Taylor (*Trans. Roy. Soc. Edin.*, 1908, 45, 397) and those of Chadwell and Anes (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 3507).

Contrary to the observations of Hatschek and his supporters, Glass and Madgin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1124) noticed that in solutions of Na_2SO_4 , down to 0.78*N*, η_r/η_0 decreases with temperature. Similar behaviour is shown by solutions of Na_2CO_3 , CaCl_2 , and salts of Li, Mg and Ca at all known concentrations. In general, negative temperature coefficient of η_r/η_0 is found in concentrated solutions and in salts which dissolve to form hydrated ions.

In connection with a thesis (unpublished) on supersaturated solutions, the viscosity of a large number of aqueous solutions of substances of varying nature has been studied. This offered an opportunity to study the question of variation of η_r/η_0 with temperature in a little more detail and also to examine the state of affairs in supersaturated solutions.

EXPERIMENTAL

The measurements of viscosity were carried out by the method of Scarpa (*Gazzetta*, 1910, 40, 271), as modified by Forrow (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 347) and Taimini (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1928, 32, 604). In this method, the measurement of the density of the solution is not required, the viscosity being given by the equation

$$\eta = K \frac{t_1 t_2}{t_1 + t_2}$$

where t_1 is the time required for sucking the liquid under a known pressure and t_2 , that of the fall under the atmospheric pressure and K is a constant which depends upon the dimensions of the viscometer. The density occurs only in the term used for kinetic energy correction (which is very small as compared to the first term) and hence a slight

inaccuracy in the density measurements does not affect the results to any appreciable extent. The corrected viscosity η_c is given by the equation

$$\eta_c = K \frac{t_1 t_2}{t_1 + t_2} - N \rho \frac{t_1^2 + t_2^2}{t_1 t_2 (t_1 + t_2)}$$

Hence this method is specially suitable to supersaturated solutions where the measurement of density below the saturation temperature is sometimes impossible and is always very difficult. Although the method is not very reliable for dilute solutions (cf. Chatterji and Vaish, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 6), it is quite suitable for solutions investigated here.

From the experimental results obtained by the above method the values of η_s/η_0 have been calculated for two different concentrations at various temperatures. Some data of Taimini (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1939, 33, 56) have also been utilised to calculate the relative viscosity. Table I gives the results thus obtained.

TABLE I

 η_s/η_0 at

Substance.	Conc.*	30°.	35°	40°.	45°.	50°.	55°.	60°.
1. KCl	37.4	1.117	1.142	1.169	1.195	1.227	1.248	—
	41.4	—	—	1.214	1.248	1.266	1.284	1.313
2. KBr	70.5	1.080	1.112	1.150	1.180	1.210	1.242	—
	82.5	—	—	—	1.253	1.302	1.317	1.347
3. KI	153.0	1.212	1.252	1.290	1.338	1.379	1.422	—
	168.4	—	—	1.397	1.448	1.505	1.530	1.565
4. KNO ₃	54.0	1.1185	1.215	1.249	1.274	1.302	1.311	—
	72.6	—	—	1.410	1.445	1.474	1.510	1.545
5. KClO ₃	12.3	—	1.007	1.024	1.030	1.036	1.041	—
	19.7	—	—	—	—	1.068	1.075	1.090
6. KBrO ₃	0.88	0.998	1.000	1.024	1.030	1.036	1.037	—
	1.47	—	—	—	1.069	1.073	1.076	1.085
7. KIO ₃	10.99	1.079	1.081	1.084	1.085	1.093	1.096	—
	16.43	—	—	—	1.149	1.149	1.149	1.158
8. K ₂ SO ₄	12.6	1.168	1.175	1.184	1.196	—	1.209	—
	17.1	—	—	1.278	1.296	1.299	1.301	1.304
9. K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇	30.4	1.038	1.054	1.064	1.074	1.086	1.092	1.109
	31.7	—	—	—	—	1.231	1.236	1.247
10. K ₄ FeCy ₆	30.4	1.437	1.475	1.496	1.515	1.510 (?)	1.578	—
	42.8	—	1.757	1.785	1.805	1.834	1.846	1.878
11. NaNO ₃	92.5	3.003	3.009	3.026	3.016	2.988	2.940	—
	113.8	—	—	3.771	3.766	3.767 (?)	3.715	3.699
12. NaClO ₃	110.5	3.613	3.516	3.477	3.435	3.422	3.366	—
	139.6	—	—	4.528	4.457	4.438	4.358	—
13. Na Acetate	54.6	6.431	5.940	5.623	5.299	5.111	4.827	—
	83.8	13.73	—	10.90	—	9.60	9.175	—

* Concentration is expressed in grams of solute in 100 g. water.

Substance.	Conc.	33°.	35°.	40°.	45°.	50°.	55°.	60°.
14. NH ₄ Cl	41.89 48.00	1.087	1.126	1.169 1.223	1.198 1.263	1.216 1.285	1.253 1.311	— 1.312
15. (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	76.0 86.2	2.925	—	2.931 3.303	2.968 3.333	2.988 3.366	3.115 3.386	— 3.433
16. (NH ₄) ₂ C ₂ O ₄	7.1 13.1	1.106	1.119	1.126	— 1.234	1.134 1.242	—	— 1.257
17. K ₂ C ₂ O ₄	46.2 56.7	1.702	1.731	1.761 2.038(?)	— 2.01	1.807 2.025	— 2.039	— 2.069
18. H ₂ C ₂ O ₄	21.6 56.7	1.276	1.287	1.306	1.286 1.680	1.277 1.681	1.211 1.658	— 1.651
19. NH ₄ NO ₃	250.0 365.0	2.657	2.689	2.679 4.319	2.756 4.311(?)	2.850 4.379	2.987 4.426	— 4.503
20. Ba(NO ₃) ₂	11.75 17.16	1.104	—	1.111	1.115 1.190	1.120 1.195	— 1.199	— 1.203
21. BaCl ₂	38.1 43.8	1.540	—	1.585 1.706	—	1.622 1.754	1.628 1.759	— 1.770
22. KCNS	242.0 320.0	3.876	3.889	3.950 5.805	4.010 5.855	4.036 5.910	4.102 5.937	— 6.008
23. CuSO ₄	50.89 70.33	2.903	2.937	2.786 3.923	2.742 3.828	2.704 3.741	— 3.638	— 3.558
24. MgSO ₄	145.6 215.1	11.27	10.71 21.42	10.36 19.83	9.865 18.60	9.486 17.71	9.113	— 19.07
25. Tartaric acid	156.0 193.6	16.17	14.51 26.16	13.56 23.59	— 21.05	11.75 19.29	11.05	— 19.01
26. (CH ₂) ₂ $\begin{cases} \text{COOH} \\ \text{COOH} \end{cases}$	10.8 24.4	1.204	1.211	1.203	1.201	1.203	1.202	—
27. Pb(NO ₃) ₂	60.0	1.581	1.566	1.582 1.887	1.602 1.853	1.597 1.857	— 1.661	— 1.874
28. CS $\begin{cases} \text{NH}_2 \\ \text{NH}_2 \end{cases}$	19.94 44.6	1.084	1.087	1.088	1.100	1.105	1.113	—
29. HgCl ₂	9.60 11.34	—	1.039	1.045	— 1.058	1.047 1.067	1.048 1.058	1.049 1.062

From the data of Taimini.

		η_r/η_0 at						
		20°.	30°.	35°.	40°.	45°.	50°.	
30.	Sucrose in water	233 350	— —	296.2 —	230.7 2245	182.7 1656	92.53 1141	12.36 828 0
31.	Urea in water	120 151	— —	2.178 2.533	2.174 2.534	2.189 2.533	— 2.525	2.234 2.528
32.	Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ in water	73 119	6.761 35.05	5.875 19.00	5.526 —	5.327 15.68	5.166 14.67	— —
33.	Acetamide in water	100 200	— —	2.875 4.376	2.735 4.144	2.635 3.958	2.550 3.769	— —
34.	Citric acid in water	161 207	24.45 56.46	19.75 41.50	— —	16.64 32.10	15.17 27.50	— —

Table I leads to the following general conclusions :

(i). In all cases, where the viscosity is sufficiently small, irrespective of whether the concentration is high or low, e. g. in solution of KCl, KBr, KI and KNO_3 , etc., the relative viscosity increases with temperature i. e. $\delta/\delta_t(\eta_t/\eta_0)$ is positive.

(ii). Where $\delta/\delta_t(\eta_t/\eta_0)$ is negative, the solutions are invariably highly viscous in comparison to those belonging to the first category. The reverse is not, however, strictly true e. g. in solutions of NH_4NO_3 , $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ and KCNS etc., where viscosity is high yet $\delta/\delta_t(\eta_t/\eta_0)$ is positive.

(iii). In the case of organic solutes, data are not sufficient for any generalisation to be arrived at, although $\delta/\delta_t(\eta_t/\eta_0)$ appears to be negative at a comparatively low concentration, a fact observed by previous workers and also pointed out by Hatschek; there are enough data (e. g. urea, thiourea etc.) to show that $\delta/\delta_t(\eta_t/\eta_0)$ is positive even in organic solutes under certain circumstances and hence Hatschek's general statement cannot be accepted *in toto*.

DISCUSSION

The expression $\delta/\delta_t(\eta_t/\eta_0)$ for any particular system will be positive if the variations in η_t are smaller as compared to those in η_0 i. e., η_0 should change more rapidly as the temperature is raised. It is then obvious that the pure solvent should have more associated or complex molecules at lower temperatures and these should break into simpler molecules as the temperature is raised. The solvent (water here) is known to consist of mostly $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ and $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3$ molecules at ordinary temperatures and these break up into simpler entities as the temperature is raised. Reverse will be the case if the temperature is lowered. In an aqueous solution of any substance (electrolyte or non-electrolyte), the water molecules cluster round the ions or molecules of the solute depending mainly upon the electrical density (unless some other forces are at play) in their neighbourhood, and thus an increase in viscosity of solutions results. When temperature is raised, these clusters or solvates break up and abnormally lower the viscosity of the solutions over and above the effect due to rise in temperature alone i. e. due to increase in the kinetic energy. In dilute solutions this effect may be very small as compared to that when water complexes are alone involved (this will be clear from the 'depolymerisation' effect discussed below). Under these circumstances then, $\delta/\delta_t(\eta_t/\eta_0)$ will be positive in general j. c.² in dilute solutions η_t/η_0 will rise with temperature in almost all cases, a fact already pointed out in the beginning of the paper.

If the concentration of the solute is further raised, the amount of water involved in the hydration will be much increased and a stage will be reached when the effect of temperature on solvates will outweigh the effect of heat on water complexes themselves. At this stage $\delta/\delta_t(\eta_t/\eta_0)$ changes sign and will become negative. This is the 'hydrate concept' of Rabinowitsch (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 954) who considers that, in solution, highly hydrated salts show negative temperature coefficient of relative viscosity owing to progressive decomposition of hydrates as the temperature rises.

From the above discussion it is clear that the phenomenon of negative temperature coefficient of relative viscosity will be more common in solutions of high viscosity and in substances which form solvates with the solvent.

When an electrolyte dissolves in water, it causes a depolymerisation of water molecular complexes, as has been first suggested by Sutherland (*Phil. Mag.*, 1900, v, 50, 481) and then later elaborated by Applebey (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 2000). This effect lowers the viscosity of the system, and if the balancing effect of solvation is not sufficient (i. e. in cases where hydration effect is very small, e. g. solutions of KCl, KBr and KI etc.), it may, in fact, reduce the viscosity of the solutions even lower than that of water itself. This is the cause of what is known as 'negative viscosity' discovered by Wagner* (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1891, 5, 31). From this conception an explanation at once emerges as to why in the case of certain salts like KCl, KBr, KI and KNO₃ etc., no negative temperature coefficient of relative viscosity is observed even when the concentration is very high. They are very little hydrated and this factor does not contribute much to increase the viscosity of the system. Besides, more and more complexes are depolymerised as the concentration of the electrolyte is increased and at sufficient concentration of electrolyte, there may not be many complexes left to be broken up by the rise in temperature. Consequently, relative rise in the value of η_t/η_0 with temperature should be greater in these cases as compared to substances which form hydrates; but due to low concentration, the factor $\delta/\delta_t(\eta_t/\eta_0)$ is still positive. A rough idea may be obtained of this from the fact that increase in the value of η_t/η_0 per 5° rise in temperature in the case of KCl, KBr, KI, NH₄Cl, KNO₃, varies from 3% to 6%, where as in KIO₃, Ba(NO₃)₂, BaCl₂, K₂C₂O₄, and K₂SO₄, etc., it is in most cases even less than 1%, but in no case more than 2%. Similarly, in non-electrolytes e. g. urea, thiourea etc., which do not depolymerise water molecular complexes to any great extent, due to a very low, if at all, electric charges on them, the value of η_t/η_0 should increase, if at all, very slowly with rise in temperature. In these cases increase is always less than 1% and generally lies between 0.1% and 0.5%.

The following general conclusions, based on the conception of molecular association and depolymerisation, may be found useful in the future development of the subject.

(i) If the solvent consists of simple molecules and the solute, which dissolves in it, does not in any way interact with the solvent molecules, the value of $\delta/\delta_t(\eta_t/\eta_0)$ should be approximately zero.

(ii) If the solvent is associated and the associated complexes break as the temperature rises and the solute does not affect the solvent molecules in any way, then the expression $\delta/\delta_t(\eta_t/\eta_0)$ will always be positive.

(iii) If the solute forms solvates or associates in any way with the solvent molecules forming easily breakable molecular complexes, and the solvent consists of

*Poiseuille (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1847, *III* 21, 70), 'found that some salts increased the viscosity and others decreased it'. This statement appears in a paper by Jones and Dole (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 2950). From this it appears that the phenomenon was discovered by Poiseuille but probably he did not realise its significance.

simple molecules, then the temperature coefficient of relative viscosity $\delta/\delta_t(\eta_s/\eta_0)$ will always be negative.

(iv). If the molecules of the solvent are associated among themselves and also the solute dissolved forms solvates, then $\delta/\delta_t(\eta_s/\eta_0)$ will be positive or negative depending upon which one of the two factors predominates. If the former predominates, $\delta/\delta_t(\eta_s/\eta_0)$ will be positive and if the latter, it will be negative.

(v). If the solvent molecules are associated and the depolymerisation of the solvent molecular complexes occurs when the solute is dissolved in it, and the solute does not show much solvate effect, then $\delta/\delta_t(\eta_s/\eta_0)$ will be positive and high. But if the solvate effect is present, then $\delta/\delta_t(\eta_s/\eta_0)$ will be positive and low at lower concentration and will change over to negative when the solvate effect predominates.

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LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY, LUCKNOW.

Received February 12, 1947.